

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Availability and use of Audio-Visual Aids in Teaching Science

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Abstract

Audio-visual instructional materials are highly motivating supplements to make the teaching effective. The learning process itself is based primarily on sensory experiences. So, availability and use of audio, visual aids helps to make the science learning permanent, to transfer the learning and to understand the science structure. The main objective of the study is to find out the availability of instructional materials in the secondary private and public schools, to find out the teacher knowledge and skills to construct and use of teaching materials. The study is based on primary data drawn by observation and questionnaire on the field visited and secondary sources of data collected from the checklist and Districts Education office, Kathmandu. The data analysis procedure was descriptive in nature and appropriate statistical measurements with a sensible description of availability and use of instructional materials in teaching science. Thus, this study proved the availability and use of instructional materials more than private school with compare to public schools and the availability of instructional materials in the schools was not satisfactory. Even available materials in the schools were not used properly by teachers at the time of teaching in science. The findings and conclusion of the study will help to concern agencies. It is better to conduct such type of research studies at the national level.

Keywords: Audio-Visual; Availability; Instructional material; effectiveness; learning

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1.Introduction

Different education plans had been recommended and emphasized for the science curriculum at school level in Nepal. Science education has been provided indispensable to human being even to a layman. Introduction of science at school and higher level is not easy task in imparting meaningful science knowledge. Here comes a need of making science meaningful and significant. So, now a day's it is emphasized on inductive and analytical method to make science teaching more meaningful and practical. Meaningful and practical in science teaching refers to the visualization and intuition or the visualization touches the feeling of the learner. Hence, visual aids (instructional materials) play an important role in making science teaching meaningful and significant. It helps to understand what, how and why the science study is required. Researcher is not yet sure that any study in this field has under taken. Thus, the need of the study has been felt most urgent. To realize the benefits of audio visual aids in teaching, secondary schools need to

adopt effective methods for using and managing their audio, visual resources. Educators, administrators and policy planners worldwide have made many futile attempts in improving education through the integration of audio visual aids in classroom teaching/learning process.Hence, this study was focused on the utilization of audio visual aids and facilities or availability at Secondary School level in Nepal. Students of school level think in terms of concrete materials. So the effectiveness of the science teaching depends upon the availability and use of audio visual teaching materials in the classroom (Gautam,2000). The learning process itself is based primary or secondary experiences. The audio visual aids provide the students auditory and visual experiences, which promote the learning. Besides this with the help of the teaching aids, the teacher will also be able to arouse the interests in the mind of student and be able to motivate them to the learning process. Thus it is clear that the teaching materials are highly motivating supplements to make the teaching effective.